

Driving Safety & Awareness Cooperative Business Model exploiting the 5GMETA platform

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Abstract—The introduction of the 5G in the automotive sector paves the way to new business opportunities and stakeholders collaboration, thanks to the availability of new connected vehicles technologies. To emphasise the opportunities of improved data sharing, different business modelling approaches exist, depending on the phase of the data value chain that technologies are able to cover. The 5GMETA open platform aims to leverage CCAM-based captured data to stimulate, facilitate and feed innovative products and services exploring the possibilities enabled by collaborative business models. This paper describes a new business model which focuses on a Use Case (UC) on “Driving Safety and Awareness” that exploit the 5GMETA platform, and highlight its business innovation. In this context, the value proposition relies in the ability to increase road safety thanks to a better driving-misbehaviour detection, thus providing benefits to a wide range of potential stakeholders. The UC has its foundation in the real-time data collected, in a scalable and reliable way, by the platform. The main innovation that the adoption of such business model will bring is the creation of new partnerships that may be enforced by a clear definition of the profit-sharing strategy between the actors involved.

Index Terms—Business Model, 5G, MEC, CCAM

I. INTRODUCTION

The EU-funded Horizon 2020 5GMETA project is developing an open platform to leverage vehicle-captured data to stimulate and facilitate innovative products and services in the CCAM field, the 5GMETA Platform. The 5GMETA Platform is a flexible telematics platform that leverage the 5G network characteristics for pipelining vehicle-captured and generated data to traditional and new automotive industry players. In addition, the platform will ensure data privacy, security, interoperability, scalability and ownership. It is expected to have commercial and research relevance and a strong impact at different level, e.g. for optimisation of road traffic and urban mobility, for facilitating decision making processes thanks to data availability, for improving the service offering and deploying new innovative services. It will allow for the creation of collaboration opportunities between different types of actors and for the involvement of new players in the CCAM ecosystem. Potential users of the 5GMETA Platform

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can be broadly categorized as data consumers, data providers, or both. Categories that could use the platforms are, e.g.: insurance companies, start-ups, innovative SMEs, mobility service providers, apps/services developers, cities, public authorities, Mobile Network Operators (MBO), road operators, Virtual Mobile Network Operators (VMBO), Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEM), researchers. In fact, the 5GMETA Platform will allow connecting data producers and consumers by taking advantage of the 5G capabilities (e.g. low latency, scalability, etc...), thus adding new value to produced data. In technical terms, the platform will allow for the streamline integration of data and data flows into added-value services. While data consumers may need to have access to data for different purposes (data monetisation, service development, policy development, etc.), data and connectivity providers mainly need to monetise data. The data can be received directly from a 5G connected vehicle, from the roadside infrastructure, or from other sources of data like sensors, a traffic control centre or social media. Data can be static or dynamic. The 5GMETA platform is developed to be compliant with internationally accepted standards and specifications from bodies such as 5GAA, 3GPP and ETSI, main players for the 5G standards. This paper presents new opportunities and business models from valuable services enabled by the 5GMETA Platform, resulting from the 5GMETA project Use Case on Driving Safety and Security, implemented in the 5GMETA Italian pilot site.

II. RELATED WORKS

A. Literature

Connected vehicles open up possibilities for disruption of the traditional car market. OEMs and tiers 1, 2, and 3 make up the traditional automotive supply chain. Vehicle manufacturers, or OEMs, concentrate on developing vehicles, procuring parts from suppliers, and putting the vehicles together. Tier 1 suppliers work for multiple OEMs and are in close communication with the OEMs. Tier 2 provides Tier 1 suppliers with automotive-grade parts. Tier 2 consists of raw material providers. But this is about to change, mainly due to various trends transforming the automotive industry: electrification,

autonomous, shared, connected, and regular updates (mostly software updates over the air). Data and the capability to process it is going to be critical in this transformation. By enhancing the existing business models used in the field while concurrently developing new ones, the technical innovation's potential can be fully realized. In a research by Mikusz et al. [1], the following primary product developments with the connected vehicle were prominently mentioned:

- Software-based or digital capabilities, in which the product architecture is maintained but a modular digital architecture is added on top to improve the functionality of the product. In this instance, the qualities of the particular software become a part of the vehicle, which no longer qualifies as a purely physical good.
- connection-based skills and traits, where the vehicle uses embedded technologies and sensors to become aware of its environment. These include the benefits already present in the market, such as awareness through sensors and communication with other vehicles and the infrastructure, remote maintenance, navigation, localization by GNSS systems, sensor data from vehicles, traffic analytics, actuators that transform physical processes like door locking and unlocking, and more.
- The third innovation stems from the capacity to use data to build services when the physical and digital worlds collide in the automotive industry. Digital products can be utilized to generate services in the form of e-services for vehicles as an interactive effect.

New trends for connected automobile business models can be derived based on these three developments. From the standpoint of the OEMs, the overview and classification are as follows:

Complementary solution The vehicle is a physical product that incorporates digital or software-based services based on the demands of the consumer as a free first offer at the time the physical product is purchased. With a tailored offering for their needs, the customer gains. The vehicle can also serve as a hub for the sales and services offered through in-vehicle channels by the OEM's ecosystem of partners. Customers benefit because they receive more value from a single source, which is advantageous. Finally, OEMs can integrate with outside parties to provide their clients with more complete services and solutions.

Efficient customization By altering the physical product, OEMs can take use of digitized versions of items like remote or telematics services. OEMs can also rely on their value network partners that have narrow areas of expertise. Another strategy is for the OEM to make money off of specialized digital services that cater to the needs of specific customers. There is a lot of room for creativity and little conflict as a result. OEMs can also engage in mass customisation by standardizing their platform and its architecture in accordance with the requirements of their broad client base.

Open commerce To maximize the platform's capacity, this involves the participation of external partners in the ecosystem

as well as the number of contributors, complements, and customers. The vehicle may be a component of a networked system that sends requests to OEMs' connected vehicle platforms automatically. To promote industry-wide innovation, revenue sharing can also be permitted with the partners via an open technical platform. For those who contribute value-added services, pay may take the form of a commission.

Digital lock-in The OEMs can retain more customers to take advantage of network effects by employing the freemium model. The well-known "razor and blade" business model allows OEMs to make money by charging for digital services while also providing complementary physical services.

Data orchestrator If OEMs gather real-time sensor data and employ a pay-as-you-drive insurance strategy to capitalize on the market. OEMs may also become fixated on their core capabilities, such as creating their own connected vehicle services and gathering and analyzing real-time vehicle data. An intermediary platform that benefits the automotive ecosystem can be a connected vehicle app store.

Neutral server Neutral servers can be set up to make vehicle data easily available to interested third-party service providers without needing to sign a contract with a vehicle manufacturer. These servers are entirely "neutral," which means that a third company, not the makers, manages and finances them. Modern security and data protection practices must, of course, be used by these neutral server operators. The neutral server also promotes customer choice.

III. THE 5GMETA PLATFORM ARCHITECTURE

According to a recent study from McKinsey, companies that successfully entered the data vehicle monetization need to provide access to 1 to 2 TB per vehicle per each day to ensure continuous product and service improvements [2]

The new features introduced by the 5G standard are vital to allow a real-time, scalable and reliable collection of information. Besides the massive amount of data, the CCAM field asks to support different data streams with different requirements, such as video flows, real-time data flows (e.g. ETSI CAM messages), etc...

Among the different innovations introduced by 5G, the 5GMETA platform exploits, in particular, the edge computing approach and network slicing. The edge paradigm is used to ensure the needed scalability. The platform will be hosted in the cloud, but the different sensors and devices (e.g. vehicles) are potentially distributed in large areas. Therefore, each edge server will flexibly collect different data streams, anonymize them and forward information to the central cloud platform. In addition, using edge can enable the implementation of services with strong delay requirements (e.g. safety services). Network slicing will ensure the Service Level Agreement needed to transport such very different flows.

For the aforementioned reasons, the 5GMETA platform architecture [3] embodies four layers as shown in Fig. 1:

- The bottom layer called "Sensors and Devices" include all the relevant CCAM "actors" that can generate rele-

Fig. 1. High level architecture of the 5GMETA platform

vant data. Besides vehicles also Road Side Unit (RSU), sensors such as cameras, etc... can generate data that the 5GMETA platform will collect

- The “5G Network layer” will ensure the performance and the SLA needed to scalably and reliably collect the generated data. It includes the radio and core 5G network, together with the edge servers.
- The “5GMETA Cloud platform” collects all the data and makes them available to every third party, exposing open, flexible and secure APIs. This is done thanks to a dashboard that efficiently guides the users in searching and using the available data flows.
- The layer “Third Party applications and services” will host the SW developed to use the collected data. The project itself is implementing three main UCs carefully chosen to show the platform potentialities exploiting different types of data flows.

The UC and the related business model described in this paper belong to the last layer and use the data collected by the 5GMETA platform to enable a safety service (see Sect. V-A)

IV. METHODOLOGY

With a platform like 5GMETA in use, different business models can arise. The methodology used to determine business models was influenced by the viewpoint presented by Deloitte [4], which classifies business models utilizing data and big data. The business models are grouped considering the types of activities that can be performed at each stage of the value chain. The categories of the proposed business models are intended to study the transfer and use of real-time data to and

from the 5GMETA platform. Fig. 2 shows the categories of the business models derived across the automotive data value chain. Each category of the business model consists of the actors and stakeholders that can adopt the business model to gain revenues and other benefits.

Fig. 2. Business models across the automotive data value chain.

A. Data generation

Companies can gain from direct data generation with this business strategy. Depending on the generator, the data may be raw or aggregated. For a charge or a cut of the profits, the data can be made available to partners or other businesses. OEMs, suppliers, drivers, passengers, and infrastructure that gives external data are the actors that can gain from this category.

The value proposition of these models offers a collection of raw or aggregated vehicle data that can be used by other businesses to construct services. Key activities involve gathering information from the vehicular data space and transmitting

it to clients. Key resources consists of sensors for in-vehicle and environment data collection, sensors for infrastructure data collection, 5G-connected devices. Key partners are actors involved in the vehicle cloud and end-users of data. Other partners include companies along the 5G value chain. Ideal customers are big data managing companies. Customer relationships are fostered through standardized service level agreements. Due to strong privacy laws, which make the data gathered sensitive and necessary for businesses like OEMs and suppliers, there is a risk of consumer lock-in. This business model exploits traditional in-person and digital channels. Costs include 5G connectivity and infrastructure, hardware and software, Service Level Agreements (SLA), legal fees for long-term contracts, human resource expenditures, keeping up with the development of 5G technology, etc. Revenues consists of subscription-based fees for regular data access, a profit-sharing or revenue-sharing arrangement with partners, licensing, a usage-based revenue model, etc.

B. Data mediation

Here, the businesses can use the data to increase its usability for partners or other businesses. The key tasks involved include gathering data from public sources or data mining and making it more useful. Analyses, data aggregation, curation, or anonymization could all be used to accomplish this. These businesses have the option of earning money through revenue sharing or a subscription-based business model. The actors who stand to gain from this paradigm include 5GMETA, businesses that place a high priority on data analytic, and academia. Technology powerhouses, decision-makers, and technical regulators are just a few other actors who may adopt this business model.

The value proposition of these models consists in the transformation of unfiltered, raw, or aggregated vehicle data obtained from data providers into something that other businesses may use. Key activities involve gathering data from data producers and processing it using techniques like aggregation, curation, and anonymization. Key resources consists of skills and knowledge needed to alter vehicle data, high-end software that can process large data, and the human resources needed to use it. Key partners are business and policy actors of the data market, TelCo companies providing 5G connectivity to vehicles and users. Customer relationships are fostered through durable connections with companies through structured agreements. Due to strong privacy laws, there is a risk of consumer lock-in. This business model exploits traditional in-person and digital channels. Costs include 5G and paying telecommunication service providers for the transfer of data, large upfront investments to put up a system that can gather, process, and supply data, obtaining real-time vehicle data from data producers may incur in recurring fees, legal fees for long-term contracts, human resource expenditures, 5G innovation, etc. Revenues consists of subscription-based models, usage fee-based models, transaction-based models, models that share profits with clients, and models that charge brokerage fees.

C. Product and service introduction

The utilization of data by actors in an automobile ecosystem may result in the development of new goods and services. The businesses can then profit from them. New entrants, such as technological start-ups and application developers, might gain particularly from this approach as the automobile sector changes. This business model can be used by existing companies like OEMs, suppliers, public services, financial services, and other enterprises like fleet management firms, communication service providers, advertising and media agencies, mobility service providers, vehicle rental services, payment services, start-ups, application developers, etc. to generate more income through new goods and services.

The value proposition consists in enabling enterprises to develop new goods and services for the automotive industry by utilizing real-time data from the vehicles. Key activities involve developing newly unexplored data-driven services using the data obtained from 5GMETA, such as software-based apps for end users and vehicles. Key resources vary depending on the value proposition that the company want to use. Key partners depends on the kind of company using the business model, be it a spin-off, an established company launching a new product or service, or a startup. Customers are end users or fleet management firms. Customer relationships are fostered by directly offering clients data-based options with their automobiles via their own platform. This business model exploits traditional in-person and digital channels. Costs include initial setup costs, operations expenditures, costs for human resources, investments if necessary, and marketing costs, as well as the adoption and expertise of obtaining data and developing solutions over it, legal fees for long-term contracts, human resource expenditures, 5G innovation, etc. Revenues come from subscription-based fee, user fee-based channels, pay-per-use fees, hybrid pricing, freemium model, or advertisement.

D. Collaborative model

By sharing the data produced in the ecosystem, multiple players from the ecosystem have the chance to collaborate. The participants can benefit from their close-knit ties by working together. Profit sharing can be used to increase revenues. A combination of OEMs, mobility service providers, vehicle rental services with advertising and media agencies, OEMs with payment service providers, mobility service providers with payment service providers, OEMs with technology start-ups, and other players can all profit from such a business model.

The value proposition consists of various stakeholders of the ecosystem coming together to build a value network that generates profits and financial rewards for each player involved in the network. The key activity of this model involve businesses in the value network sharing data obtained through 5GMETA to use it in promising markets, concluding deals that are advantageous to both parties, and enabling advertisements that are profitable for the network. Each partner has unique essential resources at their disposal, the ability to manage data

from the 5GMETA platform and use it as needed is a shared resource. Key partners in the collaborative model are the people who make up its value network, companies under this approach collaborate closely with one another to generate profits. Main customers of this model are the final users, the value network is created to increase the profits while sharing the advantages of a collaborative paradigm. Adjacent businesses may collaborate to develop a revenue model benefiting all participants. Customer relationships are fostered by Business-to-Consumer deals with customers directly, offering them data-based opportunities with their vehicles, including extra services like specially tailored marketing, insurance services, and emergency assistance when necessary. Although each participant in the partnership may have a separate sales channel, one of the sale channels includes the partners themselves. For instance, car rental companies can supply information by getting in touch with insurance providers, media agencies, and advertising directly. Contracts are just one type. Advertising and media companies can make money by showing consumers of car rental companies adverts via mobile applications while they are driving. The use of usage-based insurance applications, direct consumer contact, or encouraging automobile rental firms to bundle insurance with other services are all options for insurance companies. Costs include SLA, legal fees for long-term contracts, human resource expenditures, 5G innovation, etc. Revenues come from subscription-based fee, a profit-sharing model, an advertising-based model, or a usage-based model could all be used as the revenue model. The ultimate gains may also include other advantages for the value network's participants, such as the development of new client channels and lower advertising costs.

V. RESULTS

A. Implementation of the Use Case

Road Safety has been always one of the main driven factors behind the development of Cooperative Connected & Automated Mobility (CCAM). This UC wants to ensure Driving Safety & Awareness (DSA), by properly detecting and mitigating driving misbehaviour situations. Given the complexity to detect such situations, the current path advocated by Automotive OEMs, Tier1 suppliers and Road Infrastructure Operators is to rely on multiple data sources, which leads to a large volume of data to be transferred in a reliable fashion, before being timely processed. Furthermore, action taken to address such situation can also lead to stringent communication requirements. The 5G network has the potentiality to allow near real-time and reliable Edge/Cloud-based detection, digestion and response to driving misbehaviour situations. More in details, Driving misbehaviour situations can be caused by a large set of factors, however, this UC tries to tackle two distinct factors and thus scenarios where:

- The driver is disengaged/no longer fit to drive due to an unknown reason reducing her/his physical capacity, and with a potentially engaged vital prognosis, therefore it is possible to speak about "Health-related Misbehaviour"

and the emphasis should be made on but not limited to "Increasing the Driving Safety" in order to prevent road fatalities and crashes.

- The driver is physically able to drive, but she/he misjudges/misunderstands road network & signs which leads to a driving misbehaviour like for instance "Wrong-Way Driving". While the primary focus here should be on "Increasing the Driving Awareness" to alert surrounding vehicles, it should not be limited to only that.

This UC will use the 5G-META platform to timely and scalably collect data from the field leading to the possibility of detect and react to the a misbehaviour. This will be done thanks to the possibility of accessing (on the cloud platform) a data stream from a DMS (Driver Monitoring System) that provides information about the driver status. For what concerns the Wrong-way Driving, this situation can be detected in two different ways (i) by an application directly hosted on the edge that, thanks to the services of a Digital Twin of the vehicle, can easily detect the misbehaviour or (ii) using the processed data coming from the video flow on a fixed camera.

B. UC Cooperative Business Model

The DSA UC Business Model Canvas presents a value proposition highlighting how misbehaviour detection helps to increase road safety. The ability of detecting vehicles driving the wrong way contributes to avoid accidents, while responding remotely to misbehaviours allows to assist vehicles in danger. The remote management guides vehicles out of potentially dangerous situations providing a solution for safely stopping the remotely driven vehicle in the closes available parking lot, detected by means of existing monitoring infrastructure (municipality camera system already present). Identified prospective customer segments include public authorities and traffic managers, law enforcement authorities, taxi and VTC fleet managers, OEM and Tier1 Automotive manufacturers, insurance companies, and road operators. Customers will be reached through focused in-person channels, such as in-sector events and face-to-face meetings, tech conventions and industry events, scientific and academic events where to showcase demos, and LinkedIn. Customer relationships will be fostered through subscription agreements, in-vehicle app and OS, app and web services. The key partners are identified in the 5GMETA Consortium Partners, sister projects (e.g. the ones related to the EU eCall), TelCo business actors and MNOs, public authorities and road operators, hospitals and emergency services, and training bodies for remote assistance services. Key activities to bring the UC to business will include misbehaviour detection, misbehaviour response, remote assistance and management, and parking lot detection. All of this will be realized fostering the potential of key resources, such as the 5GMETA platform and 5G infrastructure, the traffic management center for remote assistance, the connected vehicles continuous sensing (for L3 and L4 AD), the Driving Monitoring System (DMS), and the Driving Misbehaviour Detection (MBD) service. Costs will include expenditures for HR, R&D and product development, sales and marketing,

Fig. 3. UC Business Model

administrative overheads, IT and infrastructures setup and maintenance. Revenues will be acquired through differentiated subscription fees per customers' type, setup, and customization services, and B2B technical support.

VI. CONCLUSIVE REMARKS

UC Collaborative Business Model Innovation potential

The DSA Business Model Canvas presents innovative points mostly in its value proposition. The value proposition of the DSA business model sets forth a new concept of misbehaviour detection and risk management, as misbehaviours are not only detected, but, for the first time, vehicles are remotely assisted to reach safety. At the moment, misbehaviour events are hard to detect, warn of and react to road sensors or human witnesses detect irregular behaviour and road operators or traffic managers set out an alarm to warn drivers and activate law enforcement officers. The UC proposal, instead, aim at early detecting misbehaviour events (thanks to the 5GMETA architecture that is based on 5G and MEC computing, two key technologies for achieving low latency data transmission), helping the driver to correct their behaviour, and assist into bringing the vehicle to safety mode before a dangerous event can occur. The UC also provides a solution for safely stopping the remotely driven vehicle in the closest available parking lot detected. Indeed, their value proposition also includes the possibility to exploit the video camera stream at the infrastructure site to quickly detect available parking lots, required for the success of the rescue maneuver. The UC innovative service is called "Vehicle misbehaviour detection and reaction system". Moreover, this business model does not focus only on the misbehaving driver, but also on surrounding unknowing

drivers that through early warning of nearby vehicles will be able to stay alert and protect themselves from possible danger. The innovation relevance of the Driving Safety and Awareness case lies mostly on the impact it brings not just on a commercial level. This UC will offer health and public management operators to expand their digital proficiency, as it will boost the impact of EU social impact initiatives, such as the sister project EU eCall. Because of all of this aspects, the UC business model is considered to fall under the category of the Collaborative Business Model, as multiple actors of the ecosystems, in this case some of the 5GMETA consortium partners (UNIMORE, LINKS, and WIND3) come together by sharing the generated data. Through this collaboration, the partners can share profits produced by their close-knit partnership. In this case, the revenues come in the form of profit-sharing, such as the collaboration between UNIMORE and LINKS for the gathering and transmission of data.

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